

The Stability of Population Distribution in Moscow: Analysis Based on Mobile Operators' Data

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Abstract

This study investigates the spatial and temporal characteristics of population distribution in the city of Moscow, with a focus on the constancy of these dynamics over time, using high-frequency data from mobile network operators. The primary unit of analysis is a 500×500 meter grid cell covering the city's territory. The analysis spans the period from 2018 to 2020. The stability of population distribution is assessed along two dimensions: the spatial distribution of the permanent population and the interannual variation of daily population gradients across grid cells. The hypothesis of distributional constancy is tested through the construction of regression models, followed by a residual analysis using Geographic Information Systems (GIS). Spatial heterogeneities identified in the residuals are further examined. The findings indicate that, for a number of Moscow districts, the spatial population distribution closely follows a pattern consistent with the Zipf – Mandelbrot law, while other districts deviate significantly from this model. This pattern was further validated using Rosstat data for Moscow districts covering the years 2013–2022, confirming both the functional form and the classification of districts into two distinct groups. The first group primarily includes areas within Moscow's 2012 administrative boundaries and high-density zones in New Moscow, whereas the second group comprises the remaining, less densely populated areas. The proposed methodology demonstrates that the distribution of the permanent population across Moscow remained generally stable in both spatial and temporal terms over the study period. Conversely, the hypothesis of temporal constancy in daily population gradients is rejected, likely due to the influence of complex factors such as the evolving urban transportation infrastructure and cumulative measurement errors.

Keywords

big data, mobile operator data, urban population density, regression analysis, Zipf – Mandelbrot law

JEL codes: C01, C21, R14, R23

Introduction

Understanding the dynamics of population distribution within urban areas is a critical component of modern city modeling. Traditionally, population studies have focused on total population changes or demographic structures, often overlooking the spatial and structural dimensions of urban settlement patterns (Argunov et al. 2017). However, for a variety of applications – including population risk assessment (Tenerelli et al. 2015), the evaluation of urban policy impacts, and the regulation of traffic flows (Saghapour et al. 2016) – it is essential to conduct a detailed statistical analysis of settlement structures and their temporal dynamics. Such analyses enable the identification of stable territorial formations and anomalous spatial behaviors, facilitating further modeling of influencing factors (e.g., urban development projects, housing renovation programs; see (Badina et al. 2023)) and forecasting changes in settlement patterns over time.

Until recently, the primary limitation in constructing such detailed models has been the lack of appropriate data:

- with high spatial granularity;
- updated at high temporal frequencies (e.g., minute- or hour-level observations).

Recent advances in data availability from cellular network operators and providers of public Wi-Fi infrastructure offer unprecedented opportunities. These data sources enable the tracking of subscriber locations at fine spatial and temporal resolutions, effectively merging the spatial precision of satellite imagery with the quantitative depth of traditional demographic statistics. Several studies have already taken advantage of such data in analyzing settlement dynamics, including notable work focused on the Moscow region (Makhrova et al. 2016; Makhrova and Babkin 2018; Mayakov 2022). Internationally, comparative analyses of various data sources (e.g. (Lenormand et al. 2014)) have confirmed the high representativeness of mobile phone data for capturing urban dynamics.

Numerous studies have also addressed the broader topic of urban structure (Babkin et al. 2022b). One of the earliest and most prominent initiatives using mobile data was the Austro-American Real-Time Graz project, launched in 2005 (Ratti 2005). Leveraging data from A1, Austria's largest mobile network operator, the project successfully mapped labor migration patterns and shifts in population distribution in the city of Graz. Similarly, Czech researchers used correlations between human mobility patterns and the spatial distribution of residential and commercial real estate to classify daily rhythm types across Prague (Nemeškal et al. 2020). They demonstrated that mobile phone data – particularly indicators such as duration and timing of user presence – can reliably differentiate between residential, work, transportation, and service areas within the urban landscape.

Comparable studies have since been conducted in a wide range of global cities, including New York and Los Angeles (Isaacman et al. 2011), Harbin (Yuan et al. 2012), Rome (Calabrese et al. 2013), Singapore (Zhong et al. 2016; Jiang et al. 2017), London (Zhong et al. 2016), Beijing (Zhong et al. 2016), and Jakarta (Ruslani et al. 2019).

There are numerous examples of project implementations where mobile operator data serve not merely as a supplementary source, but as the primary and often the only reliable source of relevant information. This transition allows researchers and planners to bypass traditional data collection methods and instead leverage real-time information derived from mobile devices and satellite imagery (Giugale 2012). Mobile phone data has proven especially valuable in contexts where official population and mobility statistics are absent, outdated, or unreliable (Lu et al. 2012; Ruslani et al. 2019; Deville et al. 2014).

At the same time, the widespread adoption of Geographic Information Systems (GIS) in urban studies has significantly enhanced the capacity for spatial analysis of population distribution (Dolgacheva et al. 2022). When combined with granular big data, GIS technologies offer powerful tools for exploring complex patterns of urban settlement.

Equally important is the rapid development of open-source statistical modeling tools that integrate GIS capabilities. Software environments such as R (notably through packages described in (Bivand et al. 2013)), released under the GNU license, now offer robust functionalities that greatly simplify spatial statistical analyses for researchers.

This study presents one such approach for analyzing the “sustainability” – used interchangeably here with the term “constancy” – of the territorial distribution of the population in the city of Moscow. The stability of the underlying processes is investigated from two complementary perspectives:

- the stability of the spatial distribution of the permanent population;
- the stability of the spatial distribution of population gradients (or pulsations) across the city.

To address these objectives, the study employs methods of applied statistical analysis and cartographic visualization.

Methodology

This study is based on a statistical dataset derived from primary information provided by cellular operators, detailing the positions of network subscribers within 500×500 meter grid cells across the city of Moscow, with a temporal resolution of 30 minutes. The anonymized data were supplied by the Department of Information Technology of the City of Moscow. The full dataset includes approximately 10,000 spatial cells, each tagged with unique identifiers that enable geographic referencing to specific city areas. The data span the period from 2018 to 2020 (for more details, see (Badina et al. 2022)).

Prior to analysis, the dataset underwent preprocessing to eliminate potential double counting – such as instances where a single user possesses multiple SIM-cards. Given the focus on territorial distribution, the accuracy of subscriber positioning is a relevant concern. A review of the literature on cellular-based positioning systems (Resch and Romirer-Maierhofer 2005; Babkin et al. 2022a) indicates that the achievable accuracy ranges from a few meters to several hundred meters, depending largely on the density of base stations. Maximum precision is typically observed in large urban areas. The choice of a 500×500 meter grid was therefore made to align with the optimal spatial resolution achievable using the available data.

To assess the stability of the permanent population distribution, a subsample of the dataset was created by extracting records corresponding to 2:00 a.m. – a time assumed to represent the typical residential location of subscribers. For each month, the median population values were computed for each cell (a similar approach was applied in analyzing daily population gradients). This assumption rests on the premise that most individuals are at home during this hour, thus minimizing distortions from intra-urban movement – a finding supported by previous research (Badina and Babkin 2021; Babkin et al. 2022b). The population distribution and its temporal consistency are illustrated in Fig. 1.

The analysis of daily population fluctuations across the city was based on a derived metric: the daily population gradient, defined as the ratio between the maximum and minimum population observed in a given cell over a 24-hour period. These pulsations are also visualized in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. The change in the population of individual Moscow cells during the day, 2019, the number at 0-00 hours is taken as 100%. *Source:* compiled by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

The research methodology follows the sequence outlined below.

At each time point t (where t can represent hours, days, months, years), the population within each spatial cell is recorded as x_i , where $i = 1 \dots N$, N is the total number of cells covering the city of Moscow. Alternatively, the analysis may be conducted at a more aggregated level, such as administrative districts.

Thus, we obtain a population distribution vector (data set):

$$X_t = \begin{bmatrix} x_t^1 \\ x_t^2 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ x_t^N \end{bmatrix},$$

which, for each period t , shows the distribution of the population across the territory of Moscow. Since all cells have a standard size of 500 by 500 meters, the concepts of population density structure and population distribution across cells can be considered mathematically equivalent.

Further, if the population density structure at times t_1 and t_2 does not undergo major changes during the transition from one period to another, this means that vector X_{t_1} and vector X_{t_2} are consistent with each other, and the stability of the settlement structure over

time is observed. Otherwise, we are dealing with variability in the density structure over the period t_1, t_2 . The question is how to evaluate the consistency of the two data sets.

In this paper, it is proposed to assess data consistency using a regression model in which one data set is mapped onto the other.

Subsequently, the hypothesis of the invariance of the population distribution across the territory of Moscow is tested using this approach, both in the case of the permanent population and in the analysis of the stability of pulsations over time.

Considering both the random component of the data (measurement errors, etc.) and the randomness of possible observed changes, the hypothesis is tested using a regression test model of the following type:

$$X_{t_m} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 X_{t_n} + \varepsilon, \quad (1)$$

where

α_0, α_1 – unknown regression parameters (estimated for two test vectors using the least squares method);

X_{t_m} – the vector of population distribution across the city at a given time t_m ;

X_{t_n} – the vector of population distribution across the city at a given time t_n ;

ε – a random residual reflecting the discrepancy between the two data sets.

The less consistent the vectors are, the greater the residual component of the regression will be when estimating the parameters. For example, in the case of self-regression (i.e. $t_m = t_n$), the residual component will be zero, which is expected – as there are no changes in the structure.

The hypothesis about the constancy of the population distribution over time (for the selected interval) will be confirmed if a regression model that is statistically adequate is obtained. We are primarily interested in the coefficient of determination R^2 , which ranges from 0 to 1. A value of 0 indicates complete inconsistency between the two data sets, while a value of 1 indicates full consistency.

Special attention is paid to the residual component ε . The values of the residuals are recorded in GIS and displayed on maps for visual analysis, providing more complete information about the phenomenon in question.

Results and their discussion

The methodology described in the previous section was applied to a sample of Moscow data for the period 2018–2020. February 2018 was taken as t_1 , and January 2020 as t_2 . The overall appearance of the data cloud and the regression line is shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 displays a pronounced elliptical shape with a small number of outliers. It is assumed that the constructed regression model for the two vectors will have good statistical properties and, overall, will not reject the hypothesis of the constancy of the population structure in Moscow for the period from February 2018 to January 2020. Table 1 presents the results of the statistical evaluation of the regression model parameters.

The test results show that, in general, the hypothesis of the stability of the distribution of the permanent population across Moscow's cells is not rejected over a two-year interval (the coefficient of determination R^2) for the regression model was 0.92, indicating good consistency between the two data sets). However, analysis of the model residuals and their visualization (Fig. 5) reveals the presence of outliers. Although it would be possible to disre-

Figure 2. Visualization of components and regression lines for vectors of distribution of permanent population in Moscow cells, people (on the horizontal axis – the number of cells for February 2018, on the vertical axis – for January 2020). *Source:* calculated by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

Table 1. Regression model testing the stability of the permanent population distribution across Moscow’s cells for the period February 2018 – January 2020

	Estimation of the coefficients of the model	Standard error	t-statistics	Significance level
α_0	94.3	5.3	17.8	***
α_1	1.04	0.003	339	***

$R^2 = 0.92$
 $F(1.10087) = 114679$ **
 Number of observations = 10089

Source: authors’ calculations based on data from mobile operators. *Note:* * 10%, ** 5%, *** 1% level of significance

gard individual deviations against the background of the overall residual pattern, the clear spatial clustering of these outliers on the map suggests that they are not random.

To explore this result in greater detail, an additional analysis was conducted on the rank patterns of cells (ranking by the number of permanent residents per cell) and the corresponding population values. This approach – Zipf frequency analysis, modified by Mandelbrot – is well known in linguistics and has been adapted for use in urban demography (Pav-

lov 2020; Jingang et al. 2019; Urzúa 2000). In this study, the technique is applied to specific territories within the city (Li et al. 2009).

The frequency diagram of the rank-size distribution of cells by population is presented in Fig. 3 and clearly demonstrates two distinct modes of population distribution across Moscow's cells. Experiments with model fitting to approximate the distribution confirm the results of the visual analysis.

To analyze the result over a longer time horizon, the data were aggregated from individual cells to the level of Moscow districts. Population distribution models were constructed for the period from 2013 to 2022 (Fig. 4).

Figure 3. The rank-frequency chart for Moscow cells, January 2020. *Source:* calculated by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

Figure 4. Chart rank-frequency for Moscow districts and model values, left graph – 2022, right graph – models for 2013, 2022 in comparison. *Source:* calculated by the authors according to Rosstat data.

In terms of the population distribution model, all Moscow districts can be grouped into two classes. In Fig. 4, this is shown as the merging of a logarithmic and a linear model at an inflection point. Figure 6 presents the two identified clusters and the number of cells on the map. As can be seen, the distribution of population densities and the two clusters are closely interrelated. It was found that a subset of areas with high population density is well described by a logarithmic population distribution model, while the remaining areas correspond to a linear model. Importantly, the classification by type of population distribution model remains stable across all periods from 2013 to 2022 (calculations based on Rosstat data). The parameters of the models, calibrated for each period separately, are also stable, as clearly shown by the right-hand graph in Fig. 4.

It is worth referring once again to the results of testing for the constancy of the population distribution across Moscow’s cells and comparing Fig. 5 with Fig. 6. In this context, the origin of the outliers in the regression model becomes evident. Two different mechanisms within the settlement system give rise to patterns in the residuals. This mechanism remains stable, at least throughout the period from 2013 to 2022.

Figure 5. Visualization of the residual component of the regression model – the stability test of the distribution of the permanent population of Moscow for the period February 2018 – January 2020. *Source:* calculated by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

Figure 6. Number of permanent population of cells (left map) and clustering according to the law of distribution of cell densities of the city of Moscow. *Source:* calculated by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

During the 2012 administrative reform, various suburban territories were annexed to Moscow, forming New Moscow. The modeling conducted at the level of small territorial cells shows that these still constitute two distinct areas, despite their formal unification. This is unsurprising. The territories in question have undergone long-term development (in terms of demographics, economics, etc.), and it would be naïve to expect that their formal merger would immediately alter the demographic and economic systems formed over centuries. This type of phenomenon is known as a temporary decline in urban population density over time (Gang et al. 2019), when a city's territory expands at a pace far exceeding the population growth of the newly incorporated areas.

Let us now consider the second part of the task – testing the stability of the territorial distribution of population gradients in Moscow. The testing mechanism is similar to the one previously discussed, with the only difference being the composition of the vector X_i . In this case, instead of the permanent population, the values of the daily gradients calculated for the periods of February 2018 and January 2020 are used for each cell. Figure 7 shows the data cloud and the regression line for the corresponding values in February 2018 and January 2020.

In contrast to Fig. 2, there is no observable alignment of points along a straight line; as expected, the hypothesis of gradient constancy is likely to be rejected. The results of the regression parameter estimation are presented in Table 2.

According to the results of the regression assessment, the hypothesis regarding the constancy of the distribution of daily pulsations in Moscow's cells for the period February 2018 – January 2020 is indeed rejected. The regression model has a low coefficient of determination, $R^2 = 0.3$, whereas in the case of the permanent population distribution, it was 0.92.

Apparently, daily population changes in individual cells are significantly more complex than in the case of the permanent population, which is reflected in the marked discrepancy in the distribution of pulsations by region during the interval from February 2018 to January 2020. During this period, changes may have occurred in the transport scheme (such as the development of metro lines or modifications to highway interchanges), which likely influenced the test results.

Figure 7. Visualization of components and regression lines for population gradient vectors in Moscow, % (on the horizontal axis are the values of cell gradients for February 2018, on the vertical axis – for January 2020). *Source:* calculated by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

Table 2. Regression model – test for the stability of the distribution of permanent population in Moscow’s cells in the period February 2018 – January 2020

	Estimation of the coefficients of the model	Standard error	t-statistics	Significance level
α_0	111.5	1.79	62.4	***
α_1	0.52	0.008	68.1	***

$R^2 = 0.31$
 $F(1.10252) = 4634^{**}$
 Number of observations = 10254

Source: authors’ calculations based on data from mobile operators. *Note:* * 10%, ** 5%, *** 1% level of significance

There is another important consideration. For the calculations, median values of daily pulsations for each entire month were used, including weekends and holidays. It was assumed that such differences would be averaged out and would not affect the test results. However, it is possible that the structure of pulsations proved to be more complex. Measurement errors may also have influenced the outcome, although they were not as critical in the case of the permanent population.

Figure 8 shows a cloud of data for timestamps (each half-hour interval starting at midnight is indexed from 0 to 48), indicating when the minimum and maximum values of the

population in Moscow's cells are reached. These minimum and maximum values are components of the daily gradient. As part of an additional analysis of the source of instability in daily gradients over the study period, the stability of the timestamps corresponding to the maximum and minimum population values for the period 2018–2020 was examined. The result for timestamps turned out to be more stable, which supports the hypothesis about the consistency of the functional roles of individual territorial cells in Moscow during 2018–2020. Consequently, the instability of the pulsations is largely determined by changes in the absolute values of the maximum and minimum population during the period under review, likely influenced by transformations in Moscow's transport infrastructure.

Figure 8. Visualization of components and regression lines for time stamp vectors of the maximum population of Moscow cells (o) and the minimum (+) (on the horizontal axis – the timestamp values for February 2018, on the vertical axis – for January 2020). *Source:* calculated by the authors based on data from mobile operators.

Conclusions

This paper presented one of the possible approaches to analyzing the constancy of the processes occurring in the settlement system of Moscow. The hypothesis of process stability was reduced to the estimation of regression equations for the periods of interest. The test can be applied at various levels of data aggregation, and in this case, databases from cellular operators with high fragmentation and frequency were used. The use of high-frequency and detailed databases allowed for assessing not only the stability of population distribution across Moscow over time but also the stability of daily fluctuations, which would not have been possible using traditional Rosstat data.

Data analysis at the small cell level allows the results to be linked to various urban planning programs in the future. This will enable the assessment of the consequences of certain decisions in urban spatial planning and design and allow for comparisons with expected results.

The application of the developed approach demonstrated that, in general, during the period under review, the population distribution across the city is quite stable, but it is characterized by two distinct density distribution models that have remained unchanged since 2013. For the identified clusters, models based on the Zipf – Mandelbrot relationship and a linear model were evaluated.

Considering these two clusters enables the construction of more accurate inertial predictive models for each, with one model being logarithmic in nature and the other linear.

While changes in the population settlement system are slow, a different situation is observed in the dynamics of urban cells. No close statistical relationships were found between daily population fluctuations across cells over the two-year period. This can be attributed to the relatively faster economic changes in Moscow and the districts of New Moscow, the development of transport infrastructure, and the changing functional roles of individual cells.

As a further development of the results obtained, it is of interest to form a model of the city's population distribution using classical models, such as Clark's model, as well as various new models (Martori and Suriñach-Caralt 2001), which would allow for a qualitative explanation of the observed patterns.

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